

ABOUT A RARE PART OF OUR NATIONAL VALUES - NATIONAL GAMES

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Abstract. *In this article, the history of folk games with a centuries-old history, opinions about their being the most important means of education are covered by the author.*

Keywords: *ritual, culture, value, tradition, pastime, national games, "kurash", "kupkari", "chilik", "hiding".*

It is known that one of the important ethnographic signs that distinguish each nation from another is its rituals. Ritual is a social event that occurs through material and spiritual demands and needs in human life. Any ritual is created and lives by embodying the main signs indicating the level of socio-economic, political and cultural development of a particular nation at a certain stage of historical development. In other words, a ritual is a life event with symbolic actions that are generally accepted.

Since the last quarter of the 20th century, ethnologists and social anthropologists have paid special attention to the study of rituals as a phenomenon of national culture, and the scientific research carried out within this topic has begun to be recognized as one of the current topics in science.

Especially in recent decades, the processes of globalization at the world level cause the issue of researching the factors of preservation of ethnic characteristics and national rituals to be put on the agenda in the form of urgent problems. The material and spiritual culture created by mankind is a whole. Religion, history, philosophy, values, traditions and rituals are the branches of this great tree, and the people's creativity, worldview and intellectual discoveries are its roots.

Along with other nations of the world, the cultural values and spiritual heritage of the Uzbek people have served as one of the spiritual hearths of the East for thousands of years. In addition, the region in which we live is a region of extremely diverse religious beliefs, religions, cultures and ways of life. In a word, the territory of Uzbekistan is one of the cradles of civilization not only of the East, but also of the whole world. As stated by the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan I. Karimov, great scholars, noble scholars, scholars, politicians, and generals have grown from this ancient and blessed soil. The foundations of religious and worldly sciences were created and polished on this land.

As we know, folk games are a special genre of folk art and have a centuries-old history. Games are created by the people and reflect the events and incidents of people's daily life. Embodying impressions, observations, experiences and emotions, he embodied the forms of words, music, and dance. Also, games have never been a pastime, but considered the most important educational tool for a person from infancy to adulthood. From infancy to adulthood, life events, natural phenomena, the power of words, and human relations are taught through games.

Until now, the Uzbek people celebrate their festivals with great spectacles. For example, folk games were widely used at public performances, parades, Navruz, and Harvest holidays. During the games, competitions and sports such as "Crowd race", "Chasing the girl", "Wrestling",

"Overturning", "Kopkari", "Doppi yashir", "Eshak mindi" are being held. In most of the Uzbek folk games, trumpets, trumpets, drums, and cymbals are used as national musical instruments.

Among our national games, there are a lot of seasonal games as well as motorized, mobile, professional games. Because our ancestors who have lived before us paid attention to the unity and continuity of games in the all-round development of a person. Among them, games suitable for all seasons of the year have been invented. Spring games were played in broad meadows, along streams, and in the mountains. This is the harmony of human spirit with nature. Because the beautiful freshness of nature contributes to the fun of playing games.

The beauty of nature is reflected in the clothes chosen for the games. The single-breasted dresses worn by boys are embroidered in a brocade style. Some people prefer a rainbow glitter dress. And for girls, there is no better dress than brightly colored silk, satin dresses, printed hats. Such a dress alone will steal the soul of a person.

In fact, folk games originated in very ancient times as a component of primitive rituals and ceremonies, which are one of the oldest elements of the thought of our ancestors. Over time, the games included in such rituals lost their ritual character and became a means of entertainment. Traditional games played by children include "Chillik", "Argymchok", "Ashiq", "Ko'mak", "Aq suyak", "Bobaltaka", "Bekinmachok", "White poplar, blue poplar", "Quvlashmachok", "Zimziyo"., "Kurash", "Kopkari" game types are included. Some games are seasonal games, played as winter passes and spring arrives, while others are played year-round.

Play is the primary activity of children. Children adapt to life through play. It serves to educate the qualities of agility, endurance, creativity, enthusiasm, and strength in them. Uzbek games are designed for children and adults. In children's games, qualities that lead to light humor, competition, and team unity are more noticeable. Bravery, bravery, honesty and intelligence are required in each of our national games.

Children's games can be classified according to the process of emergence as follows:

- hunting games (Gang, Jambil, Lappak, Ashiq, Khappak, Chirgizak and others);
- shepherd's games (Ballstone, Lifting stone, Goat game, Shepherd and jackal, Walking stick, Chillik, Podachi, Chanta, Chuv-chuv and others);
- crafts games (Dandarak, Charxpalak, Five fingers, Paqillaq, Lanka, Chichiriq, Uzuk soldi, Varrak, Barber, Eye gardens and others);
- farming games (Plaxman, John the Baptist, Soman spedi, Chanak Oyrin, Peach Sugar, Watchman and others);
- imitation games (Hola-Khola, Topalaq, Who's Who, Bear Game, Cockfight, Lame Crane, Bosari, Bees, Geese and others);
- action games (Cho'nka shuvok, Grass throwing, Who's fast, Hurkach, Tufaloq, Chori chambar, Cat-mouse, Wooden foot, Durra svet, Halinchak and others);
- word games (Who is quick, Balkan-balkan, Batman-batman, Juftmi-taq, White rabbit is a sign, White poplar, kokterak, Pirr etdi and others);
- group games (Speaking game, Heel game, King-minister, King-thief, Arshi alo and others);
- wrestling and related games (National wrestling, wrestling, shoulder wrestling, waist wrestling, etc.);
- riding games (Chavgon, Uloq-kopkari, Pedestrian race, Golden cocoon, Shoguloq, Girl chase, Eshak mandi and others).

Currently, a lot of work is being done to popularize national games. In particular, folk games are included in the subject "Physical culture" taught in general schools, higher and secondary special educational institutions.

In short, the national games of the Uzbek people have a long past, a rich history, are passed down from ancestors to generations, and are considered one of our spiritual wealth and values. Our national game has its place. It is a necessary requirement of today to promote young people to a healthy way of life by promoting a number of national games that are being forgotten, and to popularize the ancient folk games that serve to grow physically fit together with their intellectual potential.

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